

RESEARCH FUEL CELLS TECHNOLOGY BASED BY HYDROGEN GENERATOR USING SIMULATION

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Abstract

At present time many countries are searching for a new source of energy, and one of the cleanest energy sources is Fuel Cells. A Fuel Cell is an electric-chemistry device, that converts a gas to electric power. Fuel Cell that known in the present were, Alkali fuel cell, Polymetric electrolyte membranes, phosphoric acid, molten carbonate, microbial, and solid oxide. Besides the method, fuel cell technology has a long-range work temperature, from room temperature to 1000°C. This paper will explain fuel cell technology using an Hydrogen Generator, in this method using Hydrogen and oxygen to produce an electrolyte, waste from this reaction was heat air and water vapor. Besides that water vapor can be used as a power source. It can stroke the generator fan, many research combine the fuel cell and water vapor/heat stream generator as a hybrid power source. In this simulation we use 2 different grid one used a AC and one use DC Grid, and for the result we was representing a power productivity, summary cost, schematic grid, and emissions calculated. For the electricity production

Keywords: Fuel Cells, Clean Energy, Renewable Energy

1. INTRODUCTION

Electricity is one of the primary energy for human life, humans use electricity to help their lives, to powered devices, and to turn on lights, stoves, and water pumps. Present humans use electricity to powered up his vehicles, like bikes, cars, and a drone. But as time went fuel oil, natural gas, and coal were draining to empty, besides that the World Union was published the climate issues, and one of the biggest giver is user of coal and fuel oil. Start from that issue many countries researching on renewable energy. Like water, wind, gas stream, sunlight, and many more. One of the renewable energy was called a fuel cell. Fuel cell converted chemical energy stored into electrical energy, using electrochemical process. The fuel cell have many methods to produce electrical energy,

and one of the methods was reduction and oxidation.

Figure 1 : Basic Principles of Hydrogen Fuel Cells

- A. Membrane-Electrode Assembly
- The first layer of MEA is named proton exchange membrane (PEM), PEM was sandwiched between 2 layers of electrodes (Anode and Cathode). Main function of PEM is conducting the proton, separating

fuel oxide, and insulating proton, the ideal PEM should exhibit a high proton conductivity rate, proper water content and gas molecular permeability, good electromechanical stability, with ideal characteristic decomposition temperature (250-500°C), water absorption rate (2,5-27,5 H₂O/SO₃H), and conductivity range (10⁻⁵-10⁻²S cm⁻¹). The second layer is Gas Diffusion Layer (GDL). GDL has provides the channel of electrode. The anode is negative electrode which the hydrogen was fueled and the cathode is positive electrode fueled by oxygen. The hydrogen in anode was split into protons (H⁺) and electrons (e⁻) through catalyst process. electron, and discharge water generating the reaction. The GDL consist of carbon, water, alcohol, polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), or another hydrophobic substance. The MEA has a three generations of development, the development. From this development MEA has increasing the demand for large scale of proton exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFCs), besides that the development was improving the performance of MEA, lifespan of membrane and reducing the cost.

Figure 2: Basic Principles Membrane-electrode assembly

B. Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells (PEMFC)

PEMFC uses a polymer electrolyte membrane as the proton exchange membrane, besides that, PEMFC also uses a platinum-based catalyst to split the hydrogen molecule into proton and electron. PEMFCs are the most common type of fuel cell technologies, are used in automobile and stationary industries to power the generator.

Figure 3: Basic Principles Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells (PEMFC)

C. Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFC)

SOFC have high work temperature (600°-1000°C), on high temperature the reaction of molecule can be more efficient, but also using materials that have a high durability, it use solid oxide electrolyte not polymer membrane. SOFC are commonly uses in large-scale of power generator, like on building or industrial facilities.

Figure 4: Basic Principle Solid Oxide Cells (SOFC)

D. Alkaline Fuel Cells (AFC)

Compared with another fuel cells technologies, The AFC was more limited users, it's because the AFC was using an alkaline

electrolyte instead of an acidic, the AFC also using pure hydrogen and oxygen gases for the reactions. Besides that, the AFC use a lower work temperature (60°-90°C). AFC actually used in space exploration and submarine propulsion.

Figure 5: Basic Principles Alkaline Fuel Cells (AFC)

2. Advantages of Fuel Cells

A. Zero Emissions

Fuel cells technologies just make water vapor as the waste byproduct, it making them zero emissions technology, also have a high attracting to reduce air pollutions and greenhouse effect gas emissions from transportation, industrial, and energy producing activities.

B. High Efficiency

Fuel cells have a higher efficiency than the technologies before. The traditional technologies which have internal combustion engines just lose much energy on producing energy activities as waste heat. On hydrogen fuel cells technologies, convert approximately 50-60% of energy from hydrogen reaction to produce the useable electricity.

C. Flexibility

Fuel cells can produce from many varieties of substances source. Including renewable energy resources like water, wind and solar power. That prove the fuel cells offer a flexible power resources and more effective to combating climate change issue.

D. Quite Operation

Fuel cells have lower noise when it producing the energy, it make them more safety than traditional producing energy. It making the fuel cells can be applicating in urban areas, that have a lot of noise pollutions issue.

E. Long Life

Fuel cells technologies have long life operation, some systems can be achieved up to 10.000 work hours. This can make the cost-effective and durable are better than traditional technologies.

F. Quick Start

Fuel cells can be starting up faster than the traditional technologies, it make them ideal technologies for application in emergency power to back-up the energy source when they have a intruding.

G. Scalability

Fuel cells can be scaled up or down depending the specific application. It making them suitable to using in wide range application, from small portable device to large power generations.

H. Energy Security

Fuel cells is domestically fuel sources, which it can reduces depending on foreign fuel energy. And it make the energy securities improve.

I. Reduce Environment Issue

Fuel cells can helping us to reduce the greenhouse gas emission effect and improve the air standard quality, particularly in transport and power up industries.

3. Disadvantages

A. Cost

Fuel cells technologies still relatively expensive to use, largely due to high cost of platinum, which is used as a catalyst in the reaction. It makes the fuel cells is much higher than traditional technologies.

B. Fuel Storage

Many substances use in fuel cells is highly volatile and flammable, it makes the storage and handling process is special. For example, the hydrogen gas must be store at high pressure (up to 10.000 psi), while the hydrogen liquid requires cryogenic temperature(-253°C). It also makes a challenge to development in transportation and infrastructure area.

C. Safety

Fuel cells are has many hazardous substance, if they can't be handle it properly. Hydrogen gas is highly flammable substance. It can be ignited when they have crack in storage devices, also it can be exploded if they can't

handle it properly. To reduce the risk, the safety procedure must be managed and measure properly.

D. Durability

Like the explanation of fuel cells technologies, some types are sensitive to containments and require high purity substance to be operate properly. This make their durability are limit and reliability in some technologies.

E. Cold Weather Performance

Many substances in fuel cells technologies are sensitive from weather, they are must have many experiences and studies to reduce the weather effect, if that can't handle it, the performance of the technologies can be dropped. This must have a high concern to make a proper area and transportation especially in cold weather climates.

4. Introducing HOMER

Homer is an application that uses to analyze and design micro-power system. It can be use in large number of design operation, and parameters (load size, and future fuel price). In case use a Homer, because the renewable energy source was have power output may be intermittent seasonal, non-dispatchable. Homer performs three principal tasks: make a system simulation, calculate the system optimization and system sensitivity analysis. Homer can simulate many different system energy configurations, make a specifics time line (hour, day, week, and years) to determine its technical feasibility. When Homer running sensitivity analysis, it can run multiple optimization process under a range from the input. The output from sensibility analysis is to helping the designer calculating the effect of uncertainly or variable changes that can't be controlled by the designer, like a average wind power, sun power, and future fuel cost. We can see the basic HOMER interface in figure 6

Figure 6: Example HOMER interface

5. Analysis Using HOMER

Figure 7: Residential Power Consumption Analysis Using HOMER

At the figure 7 illustrated the electricity demand of residentials when people are still sleeping, in 12 at night to 5 am, electricity consumption is still low, recently in the range of 0.10kW, after that it increases as people wake up and carry out their activities. In the picture we can see that 12 noon and 6 pm are the peak hours because 12 noon is the activity for residents to take a lunch break and also at 6 pm when people have just returned from the office, they simultaneously turn on the electricity. To change the DC/AC and AC/DC systems, the author's team used a combination of inverter and rectifier with an efficiency of 95%. The boiler system uses natural gas as fuel, because Indonesia is one of the largest natural gas producers in the world and the writing team wants to use natural gas as a boiler system. For the fuel cell system itself, the author's team made it at 4kW

Figure 8: Schematic Fuel Cells and AC Grid

A. Fuel Cells Connect to AC Grid

At figure 8 the hydrogen system not connect to PLN grid because of the policies implemented by PLN Indonesia. This policy stipulates that the public and renewable energy users are not allowed to sell electricity to PLN so that PLN can regulate the distribution and purchase of this energy as regulated in Law no. 21 of 2019 concerning Renewable Energy. Here the writing team also added solar panels and batteries as backup power when the system needs it.

Figure 9: Electricity Production Analysis

Homer simulation results in figure 9 show the electricity production from a hybrid system consisting of solar panels and fuel cells. Solar panels can produce 8,093 kWh per year, while fuel cells produce 181 kWh per year. In terms of electricity consumption, AC loads require 4,108 kWh per year. The monthly graph shows stable electricity production throughout the year, with solar panels as the main source of energy and minimal contribution from fuel cells. These results show that the system produces more electricity than required, with a significant proportion of renewable energy.

Quantity	Value	Units
Carbon Dioxide	997	kg/yr
Carbon Monoxide	0.245	kg/yr
Unburned Hydrocarbons	0	kg/yr
Particulate Matter	0	kg/yr
Sulfur Dioxide	0	kg/yr
Nitrogen Oxides	0.000761	kg/yr

Figure 10: Yearly Emission Calculated

Figure 10 show the annual emissions data from the resulting energy system. The largest emissions come from carbon dioxide (CO₂) with an amount of 997 kg per year, which is the main greenhouse gas resulting from combustion. Carbon monoxide (CO) is produced in small quantities, namely 0.245 kg per year, indicating incomplete combustion. Meanwhile, there were no emissions of unburned hydrocarbons, particulate matter (PM), or sulfur dioxide (SO₂), with each recorded at 0 kg per year, indicating that the combustion of the fuel used does not produce these pollutants. Nitrogen oxide (NO_x) emissions are also very low, only 0.000761 kg per year.

	Base Case	Lowest Cost System
NPC ?	Rp338M	Rp254M
Initial Capital	Rp292M	Rp211M
O&M ?	Rp2.06M/yr	Rp1.97M/yr
LCOE ?	Rp3,223/kWh	Rp2,305/kWh

Figure 11: Summary Cost

Figure 11 shows the total calculation of cost analysis for fuel cells and wind generators. The Net Capital Cost (NPC) includes the capital cost, replacement cost, and operation maintenance cost. The value of fuel cells generators, photo voltaic, and wind generator hybrid systems are lower than systems that use one wind generator and one biomass generator. or use an additional hydrogen generator. But this system are more expensive than a hybrid that use a biomass generator, win generator, and diesel generator. It because cost of installing and spare parts for diesel generator are more cheaper than system that we use in simulation. And for fuel cells system have a lower COE value than other system, it because fuel cells system have more lower energy production, and NPC. Because hydrogen generator that are use in this system can produce 11,26 KW/H for a day. It was lower than other system.

B. Fuel Cells Connect to DC Grid

Figure 12: Schematic Fuel Cells and DC Grid

In figure 12, the schematic of fuel cells using a hydrogen from electrolyze. And photovoltaic is used to supply voltage for electrolyze. The hydrogen stored in the tank, the hydrogen is used to produce the electricity. The electricity is distributed to the grid. With this schematic, we can see the integrated from the renewable energy and conventional energy that contributed to reduce the emission and increasing users of renewable energy.

Figure 13: Electricity Producing

In figure 12 the schematic using a photovoltaic to supply power to electrolyze and store the energy to the tank, hydrogen is used in fuel cells to produce the electricity. From figure 13 showing the result of fuel cells. The fuel cells systems produce 12,312 KWH/years, PV produce 10,069 KWH/years, and reduce for the electrolyze is 4.017 KWH/Year, PV still have 6,879 KWH/years. It is indicated that fuel cells can be fill electricity demand. The peak of electricity producing on March to September.

Quantity	Value	Units
Carbon Dioxide	0	kg/yr
Carbon Monoxide	0.875	kg/yr
Unburned Hydrocarbons	0.0969	kg/yr
Particulate Matter	0.0660	kg/yr
Sulfur Dioxide	0	kg/yr
Nitrogen Oxides	7.81	kg/yr

Figure 14: Yearly Emission Calculated

Outcome from the fuel cells productivity has a carbon dioxide emission is 0kg/years. That indicates the fuel cells can be used to reduce carbon emissions from electricity productivity. But fuel cells have other gas emissions, one of them is Nitrogen Dioxide. Nitrogen Dioxide is a pollutant that can cause acid rain.

NPC (Rp)	LCOE (Rp/kWh)
Rp1.71B	Rp18,730

Figure 15: Summary Cost

The Summary Cost from the schematic is about the NPC and LCOE. NPC from this schematic is higher than a schematic that connects to an AC grid, and cost/kWh is also higher than PLN. This can happen because the schematic uses natural gas, which has a high investment cost. The device used in the schematic is expensive and rarely bought compared to a device used in another grid, and the last reason is because hydrogen fuel is more expensive than another fuel.

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